

A Fault-Tolerant DC UPS System Based on a Battery Charger with an Automatic Load Transfer Function

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Abstract—A direct current uninterruptible power supply (DC UPS) system, designed for operation in a hydro power plant, is presented in this paper. Standard DC power supply configurations for large power plants consist of two AC/DC converters with accompanying storage batteries. To improve the system's reliability, an active fault tolerant control system (FCTS) was utilised. Aside from the two primary AC/DC converters, a third device was implemented with the same nominal characteristics, albeit with some additional advanced functions. This secondary AC/DC converter has two high-power contactors on its output, enabling it to operate (either manually or automatically) in parallel with one of the primary rectifiers. In order to achieve the high reliability of this facility, a serial communication was not established between battery chargers. Instead, a procedure for the turnout detection of a remote battery charger was utilised, based only on data from the auxiliary contacts of its main switch and the input contactor. Based on these logic conditions, an algorithm for the automatic load transfer was devised for implementation in cases when some of the inoperative primary battery chargers would automatically be replaced by a secondary AC/DC converter operating in a "hot reserve".

Index Terms—AC/DC converter, Fault-tolerant control system (FTCS), Uninterruptible power supply (UPS), Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN previous years, the area of static uninterruptible power supply systems (UPS) demonstrated intensive technical progress [1]-[2], especially due to a reduction in power converters' weight and size [3]. Furthermore, there were increased demands for highly reliable power converters [4]-[5]. One way to improve the reliability of power supply is to implement fault-tolerant control systems (FTCS) capable of continually operating after a failure has occurred. Some authors divide these systems into passive (PFTCS) and active fault-tolerant control systems (AFTCS) [6]. Usually, passive FTCS (PFTCS) means ordinary redundant systems, such as modular power converters in N+1 configurations (with at least one spare module), enabling the power converter to continue its operations with nominal load even in the case of module failures. Therefore, modular construction with reserve modules is a frequent topology for modern power converters in industrial UPS systems. Nonetheless, often PFTCS are not

even considered to be true fault-tolerant systems, since it is not possible to isolate the failure or continue device operations with modified characteristics [6]. Therefore, if a customer has high demands for the secure operation of their power plant, among the first requests would be highly reliable UPS devices, particularly in the case of DC voltage. Accordingly, the implementation of redundant batteries and active fault-tolerant AC/DC converters would be strongly justified.

Another important issue is to realise a simple and reliable state diagnostic of a primary ("master") battery charger. If such a diagnostic relies on a serial communication, it would depend on the regular operation of a battery charger control unit. Nevertheless, in the case of a battery charger control unit fault, or the loss of its power supply voltage, a serial communication would simultaneously fail. Consequently, it would be preferable to develop some mode of diagnostics that could solely rely on a secondary ("slave") battery charger, not depending on the correctness of a primary charger operation. Nonetheless, such a method, with few available signals, should be capable of reliably detecting the state of the monitored device, avoiding both false alarms and oversight of real faults.

In this paper, an active fault-tolerant DC UPS system was presented, implemented in the "Djerdap 2" hydro power plant. A detailed description was given of a method for fault diagnostics in primary battery chargers, as well as a utilised automatic transfer function.

II. BATTERY CHARGERS

A. DRI-PT Series of Thyristor AC/DC Converters

Owing to the implemented design, based on a programmable logic controller (PLC) and a touch-sensitive human machine interface (HMI), this specific kind of AC/DC converter distinguishes itself among other thyristor rectifiers, made in the second half of the previous decade. The devices of the DRI-PT series are rectifiers developed in the "Nikola Tesla" Electrical Engineering Institute, designed to be implemented as battery chargers in UPS systems [7]-[9]. Seven thyristor rectifiers were produced in three lots (based on mutually significantly different designs) and commissioned in three hydro power plants (HPP) in Serbia: "Djerdap 2" [7], "Bajina Bašta" [8] and "Djerdap 1" [9].

All of these three types of AC/DC converters had different circuit topologies to achieve fault-tolerant operations. The original devices (DRI 220-70PT) were configured to operate

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as two battery chargers with accompanying storage batteries, keeping a third battery charger, without its own battery, in a “hot reserve” [7].

The second system, comprised of two rectifiers DRI 48-50PT, was commissioned in the “Bajina Bašta” HPP [8]. This was preferably PFTCS, with a single battery charger and redundant DC load power supply. The thyristor rectifier was expanded with 100% redundant DC/DC converters in its output stage, supplying critical loads with a nominal voltage of 48 V for numerous possible variations in battery voltage (between 36 V and 75 V) [8].

The third system was the most complex of all, forming a conjoint facility of two AC/DC converters (DRI 220-160PTD) and a DC distribution board with two mutually independent busbar systems, designed for “Djerdap 1” HPP [9]. The DRI 220-160PTD line-frequency phase-controlled rectifiers have a two-channel control system, a primary from a PLC microprocessor unit, and a secondary from an analogue PI controller, activating in cases of PLC failure [9].

B. Construction of DRI 220-70PT AC/DC Converters

DRI 220-70PT Rectifiers (Fig. 1) are line-frequency self-commutated power converters, with a thyristor half-bridge serving as an actuator, designed for nominal output parameters of 220 V and 70 A. These AC/DC converters were foreseen for use in lead-acid or nickel-cadmium storage battery charging, as well as the power supply of a critical DC load (either with or without a connected storage battery) in an additional facility of the “Djerdap 2” HPP (situated on the border between Serbia and Romania, on the river Danube). There are “master” (DRI 220-70PTM) and “slave” (DRI 220-70PTS) varieties of these AC/DC converters, with the “slave” type being somewhat more complex (see Fig. 2). Three DRI 220-70PT rectifiers, together with two lead-acid storage batteries, represent the UPS system for a load operating with 220 V DC safety voltage in the power plant (presented in Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. DRI 220-70PTM1 (left), DRI 220-70PTS (in the middle) and DRI 220-70PTM2 (right) AC/DC converters in an additional facility of the “Djerdap 2” HPP.

The control unit is primarily based on the “Omron” CJ1-series PLC. Analogue circuits and drivers, specific to the line-frequency self-commutated rectifiers, were separately consolidated on the “DIGISP 06” motherboard. Occupying the role of the human-machine interface (HMI) was the “Omron” NS5 touch panel, replacing all the push-buttons, instruments and switches (except the main switch) on the AC/DC converter’s cabinet front door. Above the HMI, the 20-diode LED panel was mounted.

Fig. 2. Interior appearance of the DRI 220-70PTM1 (left) and DRI 220-70PTS (right) AC/DC converters. Note the two output contactors in the upper back field of the “slave” device.

Fig. 3. Simplified schematic circuit diagram of the DC UPS system installed in the “Djerdap 2” HPP. While every battery charger has its input contactor (IC), the output contactors (OCS1 and OCS2) are only part of the DRI 220-70PTS “slave” battery charger. Note the auxiliary contacts of the main switches (AU.SW.M1 and AU.SW.M2) and input contactors (AU.ICM1 and AU.ICM2) of two “master” rectifiers.

When an input contactor is turned off, the power circuit of a battery charger is isolated from the mains grid voltage. As soon as the main switch (on the front door of a battery charger cabinet; see Fig. 1) is turned on, the input contactor activates, connecting a power circuit to the mains grid voltage (3 x 400 V, 50 Hz). Nonetheless, the battery charger is only turned

on after the activation of the virtual “START” taster on an HMI panel.

At an HMI panel, user can make wide variations of the preset parameters, such as the modes of operation, references of output voltage and current, thresholds of overvoltage and undervoltage protections, load transfer options, as well as parameters of PI controllers. A variation of the reference voltage is a particularly important function in the case when one or more battery cells were short-circuited. Rectifier may charge the battery with the reference voltage even if some of battery cells are missing, but this shouldn't be performed for a long time. In such a case, referent voltages in all modes of the battery charging operation (float, boost and equalizing charge) should be reduced, in order to prevent the battery damage due to the operation with excessive voltage. Thus, for all the battery chargers, it is important to operate with the same number of battery cells. The secondary battery charger can have only one set of reference voltages, for the one exact number of the storage battery cells. Therefore, in order to permanently keep active the automatic load transfer function of the secondary battery charger, both storage batteries should have the same number of the short-circuited cells. Nonetheless, it should be noted that the short-circuiting of the storage battery cells is an improvisation that should be avoided if not necessary, and that the spare battery cell should be mounted as soon as possible after the perceived failure of a storage battery string.

In order to enable autonomous operation of all battery chargers of the “DRI-PT” series, they do not have measurement data on the output current of other rectifiers in the same facility. Thus, these rectifiers do not have a possibility for equal current sharing during the parallel operation. Usually, for the same values of the reference voltages, the DRI 220-70PT battery chargers should perform some division of the total load current. Nonetheless, there is no chance for overload of any of the parallel operating rectifiers. In the worst case, if the total output current is too high, one battery charger would reach the current limit, while the other would take the remaining load. All the battery chargers were dimensioned to operate with the nominal load current for the entire operational life, that is, at least, twenty years.

DRI 220-70PT rectifiers have multiple monitoring and test functions implemented, such as a battery presence check and the service mode of operation. There are also several fault detection procedures, either for failure of the complete power devices (rectifiers or storage batteries) or just parts of a battery charger. The former procedures are primarily related to the secondary device DRI 220-70PTS to detect fault (or its cessation) of either of the primary devices. The latter procedures are related to all AC/DC converters, since there is a need to detect either unacceptable operation states or failures that affect the device's operation but can be tolerated (earth fault, low output voltage, etc.).

There are five internal states (“hard faults”) that cause immediate the shutdown of the DRI-PT battery chargers: high voltage, overload, mains voltage fault, high output voltage ripple and drive pulse loss (or the total thyristor bridge failure – described in the following section). If a shutdown happens

(excluding cases of mains voltage fault), thirty seconds later an automatic restart begins and the rectifier enters the soft-start phase, gradually increasing the output voltage. If the cause of failure ceases to exist, after another 30 seconds the soft-start phase is over and the device reaches the preset nominal output voltage. If the cause of failure is still present, rectifier protection will react and the device would again be turned off. There is a programmed procedure for three automatic restarts: if after the third attempt the rectifier protection reacts intermittently, the automatic restart procedure is discontinued and the input mains contactor is turned off, leaving an inoperative AC/DC converter without mains voltage power supply.

III. DETECTION OF FAULTS

A. Internal Detection of a Thyristor Bridge Fault

If the failure of some of the actuator's elements occurs (such as particular thyristor or ultrarapid fuse), an AC/DC converter may continue its operation, though with degradation of its characteristics. However, in order to achieve the “graceful degradation” and timely reduction of its output characteristics, fault-tolerant devices need reliable procedures even to detect minor failures.

The most common practice for fuse failure detection means the use of auxiliary contacts to provide an independent logical signal for any one of the blown fuses. On the other hand, this simple method cannot be implemented in cases of thyristor failure, let alone for every power semiconductor in a thyristor bridge.

On DRI 220-70PT rectifiers, auxiliary contacts for the detection of failures in a thyristor bridge were not used. As was first implemented in the “DRI” series of thyristor rectifiers [10], in the “DRI-PT” series the detection of the second mains voltage harmonic was utilised as an indicator of a (partial) thyristor power converter failure, or, alternatively, “a thyristor bridge asymmetry” [10].

If some of the actuator element faults occur (such as particular thyristor or fuse), a battery charger may continue its operation. Nevertheless, it is not impossible for a battery charger to remain in operation with a completely dysfunctional power semiconductor actuator. There may be many reasons for such a failure, from a heavy incident in the surrounding environment, but also seemingly trivial incidents, such as the loss of drive pulses on the power semiconductor switches (even by simply pulling out an appropriate connector from a printed circuit board). In the latter case, a battery charger control unit may continue its operations, and, due to the presence of a storage battery at the output terminals of an AC/DC converter, consequently be unable to detect such a fault for a long time. Thus, a new protection function was developed for the series of DRI-PT rectifiers, designed to detect drive pulse loss on a thyristor bridge.

This protection function operates in the following way: if the output voltage declines for more than 10 V, in comparison with a voltage reference, and if the output current in a battery is lower than 2 A continuously for a period of twenty seconds,

then a battery charger is inoperative and a signalisation of the drive pulses loss activates. Activation of this protective function leads to an automatic battery charger turn-off, with the triple automatic restart procedure simultaneously beginning.

B. Detection of Faults Occurring at External AC/DC Converters

A simplified diagram of the UPS facility, comprised of three battery chargers from the DRI-PT series, is presented in Fig. 3. If a “hard fault” (described in section II.B) occurs on some of the primary devices (DRI 220-70PTM1 or DRI 220-70PTM2), it is necessary for the secondary device to detect it. To begin the normal operations of an AC/DC converter, it is, at first, necessary to turn on the main switch. The normal rectifier operation means that when the main switch is turned on, the input mains contactor is also turned on. However, if the automatic triple restart procedure fails and the input contactor subsequently turns off, this is a sign of a hard fault of a battery charger. This simple condition is used for a primary device fault diagnostic from the secondary rectifier. Therefore, the turnout detection of an external battery charger is accomplished in the following way: if the mains contactor is off and the main switch is on, then the conclusion may be drawn that the remote rectifier is inoperative. This simple procedure enables the fault detection of a primary rectifier even if it suffers a central processing unit failure or power supply loss, without the need for the establishment of a serial communication between AC/DC converters. It also disables inadequate automatic load transfer activation, such as in the case when one of the primary battery chargers is turned off, *i.e.*, not operating, whilst without the simultaneous “hard fault” signalisation.

The auxiliary contacts of a main switch and the input contactor of both primary devices (DRI 220-70PTM1 and DRI 220-70PTM2) were wired to the secondary device (DRI 220-70PTS). The local power supply voltage of 24 V DC, from the secondary rectifier DRI 220-70PTS, was used as the command voltage for the aforementioned auxiliary contacts in primary devices, enabling the safe monitoring of these logical conditions by the secondary device. This was also a method of precise fault detection in either of the two primary rectifiers, enabling only the activation of the proper output contactor of the secondary battery charger. Additionally, if the logical condition of the primary device fault ceased to exist, this is a signal to turn off the output contactor and put the secondary rectifier into the idle mode again.

IV. AUTOMATIC LOAD TRANSFER

A. Description of the Load Transfer Function

The DRI 220-70PTS thyristor rectifier, as opposed to its accompanying DRI 220-70PTM device, has an implemented load transfer function (both manual and automatic). During normal operations, two primary devices, DRI 220-70PTM, charge their storage batteries and the supply load connected to

their DC current distribution boards. The load is connected to some of the two 220-V DC-Busbar systems, each supported with a separate battery and AC/DC converter. On the other hand, the secondary DRI 220-70PTS device operates in idle mode, regulating the output voltage and monitoring the operation of primary battery chargers.

In the appropriate menu of an HMI display, a user may select either a manual or automatic load transfer. Before the option of a manual load transfer is activated, a user has to select, by pressing virtual tasters on an HMI panel, the secondary device connection either to the first (DRI 220-70PTM1) or the second (DRI 220-70PTM2) of the primary AC/DC converters. Thus, the activation of a manual load transfer leads to the immediate connection of a secondary battery charger to one of the selected primary devices. Connection is established using one of two output contactors in rectifier DRI 220-70PTS. Rectifier DRI 220-70PTS therefore operates in parallel with one of the selected DRI 220-70PTM devices. If a virtual switch for a manual load transfer is turned off, the secondary DRI 220-70PTS rectifier disconnects from its primary rectifier and returns to the idle mode of operation.

More importantly, there is also the possibility of users choosing the automatic load transfer function. If the automatic load transfer function is active, the secondary device monitors the operation of the two primary battery chargers. If either of the primary devices endures a “hard fault” and the automatic triple restart fails, the mains input connector is automatically turned off. In such a case, the DRI 220-70PTS rectifier automatically connects (through one of its two output contactors) to the output of the failed device after the selected time delay (from one to ten minutes) expires. In the meantime, DC load is supported only by the storage battery.

In the manual mode of the load transfer, the secondary rectifier may operate with the inoperative device’s battery and load if necessary, until the manual command is given to an output contactor to turn off. If the secondary battery charger operates with an active option of the automatic load transfer, a failed primary rectifier, after the repair, resumes operations, whilst the secondary device automatically disconnects from a load and a battery, after the expiration of the preset time delay.

B. An Algorithm for the Automatic Load Transfer

An algorithm for the automatic load transfer, implemented in the DRI 220-70PTS battery charger, was realised as a software function, performed by the central processing unit of a PLC. A simplified algorithm of the implemented automatic load transfer function is presented in Fig. 4.

In order to implement the automatic load transfer, several logical conditions have to be fulfilled, with the appropriate values of the corresponding software flags. At first, the “slave” battery charger, DRI 220-70PTS, has to be in a stationary state, when the phases of initialisation (F.Start = 1; Fig. 4) and “soft start” (F.Soft.Start = 0) are over. Further, no detection of any “hard fault” is allowed (F.Hard.Fault = 0), and a flag for the automatic load transfer should be active

(F.Auto.L.Trans = 1; Fig. 4). In the next step, there is a need to detect the main switches of both the remote “master” battery chargers (SW.M1.ON = 1 or SW.M2.ON = 1) powering on. Finally, it is necessary to detect the inactive state of the input contactors of two “master” AC/DC converters (IC.M1.ON = 0 or IC.M2.ON = 0). This way, when all the specified logical conditions are fulfilled, a counting sequence commences, which may last from one to ten minutes (presented in Fig. 4 utilising RC circuits). When the preset time delay is over, the “slave” device turns on the appropriate output contactor, either for connection to the output terminals of the DRI 220-70PTM1 battery charger (using the output contactor OCS.1) or the second rectifier, DRI 220-70PTM2 (utilising the output contactor OCS.2). As may be seen from Fig. 4, both output contactors must not be turned on at the same time. Finally, if any of the necessary logical conditions are no longer being fulfilled, after a new countdown sequence the active output contactor is turned off, and the “slave” battery charger again goes back into idle mode.

Fig. 4. Logical conditions for the execution of the automatic load transfer, utilised on the “slave” battery charger DRI 220-70PTS. A simplified algorithm was presented in the form of a Boolean (switching) circuit, utilising AND and NAND elements. Time delays were presented with RC circuits.

V. CONCLUSION

For implementation in the DC UPS system of an HPP, a fault-tolerant facility was developed, comprised of three AC/DC converters. In order to enable the quick replacement of a potentially failed rectifier, a load-transfer procedure (automatic or manual) was utilised in one of these three battery chargers.

In the automatic mode of operation, two primary (“master”) AC/DC converters are charging the accompanying storage batteries and DC load, while the secondary (“slave”) device operates in idle mode, simultaneously monitoring the state of the two primary devices. If a hard fault of either of the primary devices was detected, the secondary device would, after the preset delay time, connect to the failed rectifier output contacts, supplying the accompanying battery and load. If the primary device comes back into operation, the secondary AC/DC converter would, after the same predefined

delay time, disconnect from its output contacts and return to the idle mode of operating.

In order to enable the implementation of the automatic load transfer, it was necessary to utilise a simple procedure for the on-line monitoring of two primary battery chargers without the implementation of a serial communication. Such a procedure was realised utilising only two auxiliary contacts on both of the monitored AC/DC converters, obtaining data on the state of the input switch and input contactor of each battery charger. The fault detection of the monitored battery charger is accomplished in the following way: if a mains contactor is off and a main switch is on, then the conclusion may be drawn that a remote AC/DC converter is inoperative.

In order to enable the fault detection of a primary battery charger even in the case of drive pulse loss on a thyristor bridge, a new protective function was developed. It operates in the following way: if the output voltage significantly decreases, whilst the output current in a battery is simultaneously negligible, then the conclusion may be drawn that the battery charger is inoperative and the signalisation of the drive pulses loss activates. The utilisation of the drive pulse loss protection function, together with other “hard faults” (overvoltage, overload, high output voltage ripple), enables the timely and reliable fault detection of the monitored battery charger.

The operation of the load transfer functions, both automatic and manual, was tested in all phases of the construction of the described facility, *i.e.*, during the phases of development, manufacture and commissioning of the DRI-PT series of battery chargers. Tests were successfully performed with a resistive load in a workshop, as well as with an accompanying DC load and lead-acid batteries in a “Djerdap 2” HPP.

The described technical solution is not restricted only to a field of thyristor power converters but may also be implemented in battery chargers based on high-frequency, switching power converters (PWM rectifiers).

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